

Pixelated photonic crystals

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Photonic crystals can prevent or allow light of certain frequencies to propagate in distinct directions in anomalous and useful ways for use as waveguides, laser cavities and topological light propagation. However, there exist limited approaches for fundamental re-configuration of photonic crystals, such as changing the unit cell to various and on-demand geometries and symmetries. This work introduces the concept of pixelated 2D photonic crystals where the variability of the dielectric profile is achieved by a pixelated matrix of the material. Specifically, the cross-sections of dielectric cylindrical pillars distributed in a photonic crystal lattice are replaced with pixelated circles using different resolutions and the corresponding band diagrams are calculated. The comparison to the band diagrams of the original structure shows that the original—and today typically used—cylindrical design can be well approximated by as few as 5×5 square switchable pixels while retaining less than 1% change in the photonic band structure. Experimental realization of switchable pixelation is proposed based on the liquid crystal display (LCD) technology with high birefringence materials. More generally, the demonstrated approach to reconfigurable two-dimensional photonic crystal based on switchable pixels could enable realization of diverse fundamentally reconfigurable advanced optical materials.

1 Introduction

Photonic crystals are low-loss periodic dielectric media [1] that are constructed of material components with different dielectric constants and arranged into different subwavelength structures, such as slabs [2], pillars [1], spheres [3], gyroids [4], and other. If the dielectric constants of the materials in the photonic crystals are sufficiently different and if the absorption is minimal, then the refraction and reflection from all the possible effective interfaces between different material components produce interesting phenomena for photons, including selective light diffraction [5], waveguiding, [6], lasing [7] and topologically protected phenomena [8]. Photonic crystals are composed of fixed periodic subwavelength structures, which determine their band structure. Once the photonic crystal is produced, the band structure can be tuned by controlling the refractive index of the elements or their surroundings [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] by changing the optical properties of the material with nonlinear material's response [15], using phase changing materials [16, 17], applying mechanical stress [18, 19] or changing temperature [20]. Nevertheless, reconfiguring the geometry and symmetry of the unit cells of the photonic crystals beyond the tuning of the operational frequencies remains a challenge.

Many optical applications are based on pixels—picture elements—as the isolated entities of larger planar structures. Examples include detector [21] and light emitting diode (LED) arrays and metasurfaces [22]. Pixelated design is often combined with liquid crystals (LCs) where liquid crystal orientation is manipulated separately in each pixel by external electromagnetic fields in order to modulate the transmission of light by changing the polarization dependant refractive index of the material. Liquid crystal based devices include spatial light modulators [23, 24], liquid crystal on silicon (LCOS) displays [25, 26] and widely used liquid crystal displays (LCDs). In addition to display technology, LCD technical solutions were recently transferred to applications like particle transport [27] and LCD 3D printing [28, 29], where the display acts as a mask.

In this article, we demonstrate how pixelation of the unit cell can be developed to realise fundamentally tunable two-dimensional photonic crystals, including their bandstructure. The goal is to explore whether the dielectric structures in the unit cell of the photonic crystal could be constructed of pixels. Such design would allow for simplified engineering and more robust construction of photonic crystals. As a route

Figure 1: Design of pixelated approximations of 2D photonic crystal made of dielectric cylindrical columns. (a) A circular cross section of a column with the radius R is approximated by pixels. The unit cell size A in units of pixels is determined by different formulas for even and odd diameter of the pixelated column D , as shown by Eq. 1. (b) Pixelated approximations of a circular cross section for $D = (1, \dots, 16)$. (c) Radius of the circular column with the same area as its pixelated approximation in the units of unit cell size A , as defined by Eq. 2.

towards experimental realisation, we discuss the use of LCD technology for constructing reconfigurable photonic crystals by switching (effective) refractive index in each pixel separately.

2 Results

A typical design of two-dimensional photonic crystal consists of a square lattice of cylindrical dielectric columns in vacuum, which are homogeneous in the z direction and imagined to be infinitely tall. For a certain selection of parameters, namely ratio between the column radius and the unit cell size for given dielectric contrast, full band gaps are observed for in-plane ($k_z = 0$) propagation of Transverse-Magnetic (TM) modes with $\vec{E} = (0, 0, E_z)$ and $\vec{H} = (H_x, H_y, 0)$. Here we will analyze the effects of rough pixelation of the columns on the band structure and band gaps of the photonic crystal.

The unit cell of such photonic crystal has a shape of a square with a cylindrical column placed in the middle, as shown in **Figure 1(a)**. In order to analyze the effects of pixelation we approximate the cross section of the column by an array of squared pixels with the diameter D of the pixelated circle ranging from 1 to 16 pixels, as shown in Figure 1(a). “Full” pixels in black represent the dielectric material with $\varepsilon = 12$ and “empty” pixels in white the surrounding, here vacuum with $\varepsilon = 1$. The best approximations of the circular cross section of a cylinder for each D are determined by minimizing the polar second moment of the array, as described in [30] with the constraint to respect the mirror symmetries of the square. The arrays used in calculations are shown in Figure 1(b). In order to ensure symmetrical placing of the pixelated array in the middle of the unit cell, the lattice constant A in the units of pixels is determined by the following formula:

$$A = \begin{cases} 2D & D \text{ is even} \\ 2D + 1 & D \text{ is odd} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

which allows to place $D/2$ empty pixels for even D and $(D + 1)/2$ empty pixels for odd D symmetrically on each side of the array (see Figure 1(a)). Band structures of pixelated approximations are compared to the band structures of the cylindrical columns with the same area—i.e. same amount of dielectric material in the unit cell. Radius of cylindrical column, measured in the units of the lattice constant A , is determined as:

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{N}{\pi^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of full pixels in the array. Figure 1(c) shows how R depends on D for selected pixelated arrays and converges towards $R = 0.25A$. The even-odd effect, showing in larger R for even

Figure 2: Comparison of band diagrams of a square lattice of cylindrical dielectric columns with circular cross sections and their pixelated approximations for (a) $D = 1$ and (b) $D = 5$. Areas of dielectric materials in the unit cell are matched. Far right plots show the relative difference between the band diagrams.

D , occurs due to additional pixel being added to the surrounding for odd D in Equation 1, to ensure that the unit cell preserves symmetries of a square (see Figure 1(a)). Alternatively, a pixel could be subtracted, leading to the opposite effect, but same conclusions. Numerical calculations were performed by use of MIT Photonic Bands (MPB) software package [31]. The resolution in calculations was 200 grid points per unit cell in each direction and was slightly adjusted for each D so that each pixel in the array consisted of the integer number of grid points and no additional interpolation was needed.

Band diagrams for photonic crystals consisting of pixelated and circular columns for $D = 1$ and $D = 5$ are shown in **Figure 2**. Surprisingly, already for $D = 1$ (Figure 2(a)), where circle is approximated by a square, a good agreement in terms of band diagrams is achieved. In fact, there are no distinguishable differences between the two for the first four bands, which lay beneath the second band gap, marked with blue shades. To quantify that, we plot the relative difference between the frequencies of the bands in both diagrams $(\omega^{(\text{pix})} - \omega^{(\text{circ})})/\omega^{(\text{circ})}$. The results show that the relative difference in frequency is in the range of 1% for the bands below the second band gap and even below 0.5% for the first three bands, regardless of the direction of propagation. The difference gets gradually larger for higher bands. Similar results are obtained for $D = 5$, where relative differences for first four bands stay in the range of 0.5%, however also matching of higher bands is improved, namely relative difference for bands 5 and 6 in this case also drops below 1%. Importantly, for $D = 5$, only 3 bands lay beneath the second gap, compared to 4 for $D = 1$. The reason is considerably smaller amount of dielectric material in the unit cell for $D = 1$, which can also be seen from $R(D)$ plot in Figure 1(c). For every $D > 1$ the number of bands below the second gap is 3.

Next, we analyze the positions and sizes of first two full band gaps in the system. The results are shown in **Figure 3** and **Figure 4**. Position of band gap is determined by its central (mid-gap) frequency, which is calculated as the average of the upper and lower limit frequency. Positions of band gaps for different values of D are shown in Figure 3(a). Once again, we observe that $D = 1$ is a standout due to lower amount of dielectric material in a unit cell. Similarly, the reason why for odd D band gaps systematically occur at slightly higher frequencies than for even D is that the radius of the associated cylindrical column is systematically smaller for odd D as shown in Figure 1(c). In Figure 3(b) relative differences of mid-gap frequencies $(\omega_{\text{mid}}^{(\text{pix})} - \omega_{\text{mid}}^{(\text{circ})})/\omega_{\text{mid}}^{(\text{circ})}$ between pixelated and cylindrical column are shown. Remarkably, positions of both band gaps are similar in pixelated and cylindrical case with the difference being smaller than the 1%.

Figure 3: Band gap positions in the band diagrams of pixelated cylindrical columns. (a) Mid-gap frequencies of the first two band gaps for different values of D . Insets show unit cells of pixelated cylindrical columns for a few selected values of D . (b) Relative difference of the frequency in the middle of the gap of pixelated columns, compared to the frequency in the middle of the same band gap in the diagram of circular pillars.

Figure 4: Sizes of first two band gaps in the band diagrams of pixelated cylindrical columns. (a) Gap-to-midgap ratio of the first two band gaps for different values of D . (b) Relative difference of the band gap size, compared to the size of the same band gap in the diagram of circular pillars.

Sizes of band gaps are shown in Figure 4(a) in terms of gap-to-midgap ratios. Again, we can notice that the sizes of band gaps directly reflect the radius of the cylinders. Relative differences of band gap sizes are shown in Figure 4(b). First, we notice that the relative difference in band gap size is considerably larger than the relative difference in band gap position. For the first band gap the reason for this is that the frequency of the first band in point M, which determines the lower end of the gap is in general larger for pixelated case than cylindrical. Oppositely, the frequency of the second band in point X, which determines the upper end of the gap is lower for the pixelated case. The gap is therefore effectively shrunken. For the second gap the first reason is simply lower accuracy for higher bands and also that the gap is relatively thinner, meaning that the same absolute difference in band frequencies will lead to larger relative changes in sizes.

In the calculations presented so far the dielectric contrast between the pillar and the surrounding was rather high ($\Delta\varepsilon = 11$), compared to the contrasts between the ordinary (n_o) and extraordinary (n_e) refractive index—the birefringence $\Delta n = n_e - n_o = \sqrt{\varepsilon_e} - \sqrt{\varepsilon_o}$ —found in liquid crystals. Values of birefringence of the state-of-art liquid crystal materials used for technological applications are usually in the range of 0.2-0.3. When lower contrast between “empty” and “full” pixels is used, the gaps between the bands in the band structure essentially shrink and only partial band gaps (existing for a range of

Figure 5: Possible experimental realization of a two-dimensional pixelated photonic crystal, based on liquid crystals. (a) The unit cell is comprised of 4×4 liquid crystal pixels, with the size of $D \times D$, separated by dielectric shield walls ($\varepsilon_{\text{wall}} = 3$), with the thickness of $0.2D$, shown in grey. Black pixels represent the out-of-plane liquid crystal orientation with effective refractive index of $n_e^2 = \varepsilon_e = 3.24$ for TM polarization and white pixels represent the in-plane liquid crystal orientation with the effective refractive index of $n_o^2 = \varepsilon_o = 2.25$ for TM polarization. (b) Corresponding band diagram. A local band gap with the gap-to-midgap ratio of 0.06 occurs at the M point and has the mid-gap frequency of $0.423c/A$. (c) Unit cell with a different distribution of “empty” and “full” pixels and (d) corresponding band diagram.

wavevectors) are observed instead of full ones. Additionally if the effect of “empty” and “full” is to be achieved by reorienting the direction of the optical axis of birefringent liquid crystal, sharp boundaries between the regions are desired.

To experimentally realize two-dimensional reconfigurable pixelated photonic crystal by use of liquid crystals we suggest the use of dielectric shield walls, as reported in Ref. [32]. Using such setup allows for driving the voltage and reorienting liquid crystal in each individual pixel separately, without leakage of the electromagnetic field. The size of individually driven pixels separated by dielectric walls can be as small as $1 \mu\text{m}$ [32]. To demonstrate the optical features of such system we calculated the band diagram, using the refractive indices of 5CB liquid crystal ($n_o^2 = \varepsilon_o = 2.25$, $n_e^2 = \varepsilon_e = 3.24$), which are comparable to the refractive indices of liquid crystals in the THz regime [33] and dielectric walls with $\varepsilon_{\text{wall}} = 3$. For the demonstration we selected a pixelated unit cell with $D = 2$, which is shown in **Figure 5(a)**. The thickness of the walls is $0.2D$, which corresponds to wall thickness of 200 nm and pixel size of $1 \mu\text{m}$, as reported in Ref. [32]. Consequently, the size of the unit cell is $A = 4 \mu\text{m}$. Note, that we assume sharp change of the refractive index between pixels, whereas experimentally, possibly, the actual realised profile of such change could lead to scattering or coupling of TE and TM modes and would need to be optimised for actual application. The corresponding band diagram is shown in Figure 5(b). A partial band gap with the gap-to-midgap ratio of 0.06 occurs at the M point and has the mid-gap frequency of $0.423c/A$, corresponding to the wavelength of $\approx 10 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 5(c) and Figure 5(d) show how the band diagram would change for a different distribution of “empty” and “full” pixels within the unit cell. In this particular case, nontrivial photonic effects occur for propagation with k -vector pointing along the diagonal of the unit cell (M - Γ high symmetry points on the band diagram).

While presence of the partial band gap confirms that liquid crystals can in fact be used to create two-dimensional pixelated photonic crystals with nontrivial optical properties, full band gaps are usually desired. Larger band gaps can be achieved by increasing the birefringence of the liquid crystals. Additionally, higher dielectric contrast is also needed for realising full three-dimensional photonic bandgaps [1]. High birefringence liquid crystals, for example with Δn up to 0.7 have already been reported [34, 35, 36, 37]. Birefringence in THz regime can be also improved by using liquid crystal nanoparticle composites [38, 39]. With the increased interest in THz spectral range for 6G wireless communication [40], also in combination with liquid crystals for design of active devices [41], we expect that new and better materials will emerge in the future. By using high birefringence materials or composite materials, self-assembled 2D liquid crystal structures with smaller dimensions [42, 43] could serve as photonic crystals as well, possibly leading to manipulation of shorter light wavelengths. It is also worth mentioning that only a very simple photonic crystal unit cell has been used in this work as a proof of concept. Therefore, we expect that larger and full band gaps could also be achieved by further optimizing the configuration of “empty” and “full” pixels or by including insertions (i.e. static pixels) made of materials with higher refractive indices.

3 Conclusion

To conclude, we have shown that the pixelation of the dielectric features within the unit cell of photonic crystals does not have a significant impact on the band structure. Already a low resolution pixelation which only roughly matches the original structure turns out to be a good approximation for the frequencies of the lowest photonic bands. This shows that pixelated unit cells could be used to simplify the design of photonic crystals. Additionally, the band gaps are still present in the system even if the contrast in dielectric constants between the pillar and its surrounding is small, namely comparable to the difference between the ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices in some of the soft birefringent materials. Use of those in combination with pixelated design could lead towards fully reconfigurable photonic crystals.

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Table of Contents

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